

Decision Making with Machine Learning Techniques in Consumer Performance: Empathy, Personality, Emotional Intelligence as Mediators

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Abstract

Despite the importance of emotion in decision making (e.g., ohm and Clore 2002; Luce 1998; Pham 1998; Ruth 2001), research has yet to fully understand how consumers' use emotional information to make effective decisions. A growing body of research continues to focus on the emotions present in consumption situations, however a better understanding of emotional processing abilities can have important effects on consumer performance outcomes. The current research focuses on the impact of emotional intelligence on consumer decision making and evaluates the consumer emotional ability in a sample of social network users. Additionally, through the present project, empathy, personality and emotional intelligence are being measured as intrusive variables that mediate and determine the consumer decision making.

The innovative element of the current project was the application of data mining methods in psychometrics. Specifically, in order to clarify the consumer emotional decision making, were administered to the participants' five scales that have been created through Google Forms service and posted through the website "<http://www.cicos.gr/iccmi2017/epeim>". Then the collected data were selected for analysis, with relevant transformations in order to have a suitable form for the implementation of the respective machine learning algorithms included in the software package R. The administered scales were: a) Consumer Emotional Ability Scale-Revised by the present authors in order to define how emotional intelligence affected performance among consumer relationships, b) Empathy Quotient a new self-report questionnaire, for use with adults of normal intelligence, c) Balanced Emotion Empathy Scale in order to assess the emotive component of empathy, d) Eysenck Personality Questionnaire, measuring personality traits, e) Emotional Intelligence Questionnaire, defining four aspects of emotionally thinking.

Findings of the present research indicated that emotional ability predicts consumer performance beyond the effects of cognitive ability, supporting the importance of the emotional ability construct in consumer behavior.

Keywords: *Consumer Ability, Emotional Intelligence, empathy, decision making, R, Machine Learning*

1. INTRODUCTION

Emotions and personality are a key element of judgment and decision-making, as they bring important information about who we are and how we interact with others. Little is known about how emotions affect performance in marketing. Applying emotional theories to marketing has led to research centered on: 1) Emotion as a precursor to behavior, 2) Emotion as a consequence, and 3) Emotion as mediated or moderate influence on marketing relationships. What is the role of emotions in exchanges and relationships and how do consumers use emotional information to make marketing decisions? These questions remain to be scrutinized. The cognitive framework of emotional intelligence and its association with the personality dimensions of a person (consumer) has been applied in this research to give some possible answers.

1.1. Consumer emotional ability scale (CEAS)

The Consumer Emotional Ability Scale examines the contribution of emotional influences as prognostic, results, moderators and behavior mediators, trying to explore how individuals use real emotions and emotional information to perform desirable behaviors in a context of consumption. The use of emotional (or cognitive) information to achieve a desired result implies the ability to process and use this information. The CEAS controls the concept of emotional competence and the way it relates to behavioral performance in marketing. Scale based on four underlying emotional abilities (i.e., perceiving, facilitating, understanding, managing). This instrument allowed for further examination of how emotional intelligence affected performance among consumer relationships. The Four-Branch Model of Consumer Emotional Intelligence Branch name Brief description of skills:

Image 5

- **Perceiving Emotion** (Branch 1)

The ability to perceive emotions in oneself, and others as well as in faces, objects, products, packaging and other stimuli.

- **Facilitating Emotion** (Branch 2)

The ability to generate, use, and feel emotion as necessary to communicate feelings, or employ them in other cognitive processes.

- **Understanding Emotion** (Branch 3)

The ability to understand consumer-related emotional information and understand how emotions combine, blend to get her and change.

- **Managing Emotion** (Branch 4)

The ability to be open to feelings, and to modulate them in oneself and others so as to promote understanding and growth of consumer applications and relationships.

1.2. The Empathy Quotient (EQ)

The emotional approach defines empathy as the emotional response of the observer to the emotional state of another. Empathy allows us to understand the intentions of others, to predict their behavior and to experience a feeling caused by their movement. As a result, our sympathy allows us to interact effectively in the social world, push us to help others and prevent us from harming others.

Image 2: A simple model showing the two overlapping components of empathy and how sympathy is a special case of the affective component of empathy¹.

Image 6

¹ + Feeling an appropriate emotion triggered by seeing/learning of another's emotion.

The Empathy Quotient (EQ) was designed to be short, easy to use, and easy to score. The EQ comprises 60 questions, broken down into two types: 40 questions tapping empathy and 20 filler items. The 20 filler items were included to distract the participant from a relentless focus on empathy. Empathy is an essential part of normal social functioning, yet there are precious few instruments for measuring individual differences in this domain. In this paper we applied this self-report questionnaire for use with adults of normal intelligence.

1.3. The Balanced Emotional Empathy Scale (BEES)

The Balanced Emotional Empathy Scale (BEES) is designed to assess the emotive component of empathy. Typically, the empathy construct has been separated into two types: cognitive and emotional. Cognitive empathy refers to imaginatively understanding another person's thoughts, feelings and actions. Emotional empathy is feeling the emotion of another person, but maintaining a compassionate, other-focused perspective. The above questionnaire provides an indication of five components of emotional intelligence.

Self-awareness: This component provides the basis for all the other components of emotional intelligence. Self-awareness means being aware of what you are feeling, being conscious of the emotions within yourself.

Managing emotions: The second key component of emotional intelligence is managing emotions. This means you are able to balance your moods so that worry, anxiety, fear, or anger does not get in the way of what needs to be done. People who manage their emotions perform better because they are able to think clearly.

Motivating oneself: This ability to be hopeful and optimistic despite obstacles, setbacks, or even outright failure is crucial for pursuing long-term goals in life or in business.

Empathy: The fourth component is empathy, which means being able to put yourself in someone else's shoes—to recognize what others are feeling without them needing to tell you.

Social skill: The ability to connect to others, build positive relationships, respond to the emotions of others and influence others is the final component of emotional intelligence.

1.4. Eysenck Personality Questionnaire (EPQ)

The personality dimensions introduced by Eysenck are separate types of people, each of which involves a set of features traced back to their habits and their specific reactions. In particular, what is proposed is the detection of specific reactions of the individual, which will give evidence of his usual reactions and hence of his usual behavior. This will allow conclusions to be drawn for some key features of his personality. These attributes are considered as the factors that make up each of the three dimensions of personality (types). The relationship between the reactions and their regular appearance makes them reliable criteria for rendering certain characteristics to the personality of the person. That is, dimensions or types of personality are notions that include a group of related

Image 7

Image 8

Understanding and/or predicting what someone else might think, feel, or do.

* Feeling an emotion triggered by seeing/learning of someone else's distress.

characteristics, which we deduce from the study of reactions and behavior of the individual.

In detail, the three dimensions of the personality that are proposed have the following characteristics:

- **Extraversion-introversion:** One who is defined as extrovert is social, loves gatherings, has many friends, and does not like reading and studying. Also has a keen desire for emotion, does not lose opportunities, likes danger, reacts immediately and is generally impulsive.
- **Neurotism - Instability - Emotional Stability:** Neurotism refers to the general emotional instability of the individual, to its emotional hyperactivity and to the tendency to develop neurotic symptoms under stress.
- **Psychoticism:** Further exploration of Eysenck's personality dimensions has led to the observation that there is one more personality variable that manifests in the population as a whole - that is, in healthy and divergent - in the form of reaction patterns and is indicative of the possible appearance of psychotic elements. This variable was the third personality dimension, called "Psychotism" (P) and also refers to subjective personality traits.

The result of these observations was the development of a measurement scale of the three dimensions of the personality (E, N, and P) and a complementary dimension of the L, which measures the falsehood of the answers given by the person questioned during the questionnaire. The new scale, presented by the Eysenck couple in 1975, was named the Eysenck Personality Questionnaire (E.P.Q.).

1.5. Trait Emotional Intelligence (EI)

For recording, tracing and evaluation concerning the emotional intelligence was used the standardized scale Trait Emotional Intelligence (TEIQue) which examines the Trait model of EI as proposed by K.V. Petrides. The Trait Emotional Intelligence Questionnaire is a self-report questionnaire that has been developed to cover the trait EI sampling domain comprehensively. Questionnaire measures of EI have been proliferating over the past few years, and it is important to mention three advantages of the TEIQue over them to justify the focus of this research.

First, the TEIQue is based on a psychological theory that integrates the construct into mainstream models of differential psychology.

Second, the TEIQue provides comprehensive coverage of the 15 facets of the trait EI sampling domain. Several independent studies have demonstrated ability of the TEIQue to predict criteria (outcomes) significantly better than other questionnaires.

Third, the full TEIQue has excellent psychometric properties.

Finally, the TEIQue has been used in numerous studies wherein the assessment of affective aspects of personality was required. These include research in the areas of neuroscience, relationship satisfaction, psychopathology, addictions, reaction time, general health, and behavioral genetics.

The TEIQue provides an operationalization for the model of Petrides and colleagues that conceptualizes EI in terms of personality. The test encompasses 15 subscales organized under four factors:

Well being: The Well-being factor comprises three different traits: Happiness, Optimism and Self-esteem. They measure how people judge their general level of life satisfaction.

Self control: The Self-control factor describes how far people think they can control their impulses or are controlled by them. It comprises three different traits: Impulse Control, Stress Management and Emotional Regulation.

Emotionality: The Emotionality factor comprises four different traits: Empathy, Emotion Perception, Emotion Expression and Relationships. Together they indicate how aware you may be of your own emotions and feelings, as well as those of other people.

Image 9

the

Sociability: The Sociability factor describes how comfortable people feel in different social contexts, from parties and social gatherings to formal business meetings.

2. METHODOLOGY

In this paper were applied Machine Learning and Data Mining methods in order to evaluate the Consumer Emotional Ability Scale (CEAS), the Empathy Quotient Scale (EQ), the Balanced Emotional Empathy Scale (BEES), Eysenck Personality Questionnaire (EPQ) and Emotional Intelligence Quotient (TEIQue) of social network consumers. The methodology, that was adopted, consists of three concrete phases. During the first phase electronic questionnaires were created and posted through the website <http://www.cicos.gr>. Subsequently, data were collected and preprocessed from the questionnaires. The data set for analysis was consisted of demographics elements of responders, such as the gender, the birth-place, the place of present residence, educational background of both the respondents and their parents, professional occupation of parents and also of subscales of the CEAS, EQ, BEES, EPQ and TEIQue tests. During the third phase, the data set was analyzed based on Data Mining techniques and evaluate the results. More specifically, we utilized classification algorithms so as to manage to describe the hidden patterns underlying in the data. Decision trees are a powerful way in order to represent and facilitate statements analysis (psychological) principally, comprising successive decisions and variable results in a designated period.

2.1. Personality, Empathy, Emotion Ability/ Intelligence in Consumer Behavior

In international literature, the importance of emotion and traits of personality in decision making has been studied (Gohm and Clore, 2002; Luce 1998; Ruth 2001). The research is about to fully understand how consumers' use emotional information to make effective decisions according to their traits of personality. A growing body of research continues to focus on the emotions present in consumption situations; however a better understanding of emotional processing abilities can have important effects on consumer performance outcomes. The current research focuses on emotional intelligence, in personality of consumer and in consumer behavior of young adults who are social network users.

Consumer emotional intelligence is defined here as a person's ability to use emotional information to achieve a desired consumer outcome, comprised as a set of first order emotional abilities that allow individuals to recognize the meanings of emotional patterns that underlie consumer decision making and to reason and solve problems on the basis of them (Mayer and Salovey 1997). A better understanding of emotional ability can have considerable value in extending knowledge of consumer behavior. For example, it can provide answers to questions such as; how does emotional processing influence purchase decisions; which decisions do high vs. low EI consumers more readily make; how might EI influence relationships between key consumer variables such as impulsivity and purchase intention? Additionally, with this knowledge of emotional ability, we may be able to identify those consumer's who make the highest (and lowest) quality consumer decisions. For instance, consumers with high levels of nutrition knowledge who lack the emotional ability to understand which emotions are important and how to manage those emotions toward unhealthy eating, are likely to make poor quality decisions. Understanding these emotional deficiencies can provide a means to subsequently improve the quality of consumption decisions.

As far as the repercussion of personality traits in consumer behavior, recent advances in personality psychology can help us predict consumer motivation. Traits are defined as enduring and stable patterns of behavior, attitudes, emotions, that vary between individuals. Traditionally, researchers were interested in understanding how individuals differ, and so they put a great deal of effort into discovering how to measure, map, and define personality traits. An effort was made through trait theory in order to define personality traits. Trait theory suggests that personality is made up of a set of quantitative measurable characteristics or units known as traits. Traits are pre-dispositional attribute and are relatively stable (McLeod, 2014). Every personality has a unique combination of traits and given its stability, people with a given combination of traits can be expected to behave consistently across situations and over time. The development of trait theory is attributed to the pioneering works of psychologists such as, Gordon Allport, Henry Odbert Raymond Cattell and Hans Eysenck (Myers, 1995; Burger, 2000; Franzoi, 2002). The trait theory that is being examined through the current paper is Eysenck's theory. Eysenck (1947) developed a model of personality based on three traits: "introversion/extroversion, neuroticism/emotional stability, and psychoticism" (Franzoi, 2002: 398).

Researchers are now reconceptualizing what traits are and where they come from--with traits being understood as chronic motivators that drive their decision-making. For example, researchers have linked personality traits to diverse outcomes such as experiential buying tendencies, political orientation, natural language use, preference in pets, the state of one's personal living space, and even more important life outcomes such as divorce, morbidity, and occupational attainment. Some recent data suggests that people who find themselves in disease-ridden environments tend to be less open and extraverted, presumably because this makes them less motivated to explore and interact with others (which reduces the chance they will become infected).

2.2. Data Mining Techniques

Data Mining is an emerging knowledge discovery process of extracting previously unknown, actionable information from very large scientific and commercial databases. It is imposed by the explosive growth of such databases. Usually, a data mining process extracts rules by processing high dimensional categorical and/or numerical data. Classification, clustering and association are the most well known data mining tasks. Classification is one of the most popular data mining tasks. Classification aims at extracting knowledge which can be used to classify data into predefined classes, described by a set of attributes. The extracted knowledge can be represented using various schemas.

3. RESULTS

3.1. Association Rule Learning

Association rule learning is a rule-based machine learning method for discovering interesting relations between variables in large databases. It is intended to identify strong rules discovered in databases using some measures of interestingness. They are usually required to satisfy a user-specified minimum support and a user-specified minimum confidence at the same time. Association rule generation is usually split up into two separate steps:

- i. A minimum support threshold is applied to find all frequent itemsets in a database.
- ii. A minimum confidence constraint is applied to these frequent itemsets in order to form rules.
- iii. While the second step is straightforward, the first step needs more attention.

Three most widely used measures ²for selecting interesting rules are:

Support

Support is an indication of how frequently the itemset appears in the dataset.

Confidence

Confidence is an indication of how often the rule has been found to be true.

Lift

Is the ratio of the observed support to that expected if X and Y were independent.

Apriori is an algorithm for frequent item set mining and association rule learning over transactional databases. It proceeds by identifying the frequent individual items in the database and extending them to larger and larger item sets as long as those item sets appear sufficiently often in the database. The frequent item sets determined by Apriori can be used to determine association rules which highlight general trends in the database.

Visualizing Extracted Rules

Visualization has a long history of making large data sets better accessible using techniques like selecting and zooming. In this paper we use the R-extension package "arulesViz" which implements several known and novel visualization techniques to explore association rules. Below, we represent the extracted rules in a variety of ways with different techniques.

²Every rule is composed by two different sets of items, also known as itemsets, X and Y, where X is called antecedent or left-hand-side (LHS) and Y consequent or right-hand-side (RHS).

Graph-based visualization

Graph-based visualization offers a very clear representation of rules but they tend to easily become cluttered and thus are only viable for very small sets of rules

Graph for 57 rules

Grouped Matrix Visualization

Antecedents (columns) in the matrix are grouped using clustering. Groups are represented as balloons in the matrix.

Parallel coordinates visualization

Parallel coordinates plots are designed to visualize multidimensional data where each dimension is displayed separately on the x-axis and the y-axis is shared. Each data point is represented by a line connecting the values for each dimension

Parallel coordinates plot for 57 rules

Apriori rules

Specifically of our use we altered the Support and Confidence values to 50% and 90% respectively

A sample of the extracted rules (Top 10)

lhs	rhs	support	confidence	lift
1 {Sex=Woman, Educational.level=Higher education, CEAS_Q8=Content, CEAS_Q13=Hopelessness, Loneliness, Sadness}	{CEAS_Q11=Nervousness, Rebellion, Shooting.}	0.4024390	0.9166667	1.252778
2 {Sex=Woman, Educational.level=Higher education, CEAS_Q13=Hopelessness, Loneliness, Sadness}	{CEAS_Q11=Nervousness, Rebellion, Shooting.}	0.4390244	0.9000000	1.230000
3 {CEAS_Q19..Hostility.=1}	=> {CEAS_Q22..JOY.=1}	0.4268293	0.9210526	1.144338
4 {CEAS_Q22..JOY.=1, emotionality=MID}	=> {CEAS_Q13=Hopelessness, Loneliness, Sadness}	0.4756098	0.9750000	1.142143
5 {Sex=Woman, emotionality=MID}	=> {CEAS_Q13=Hopelessness, Loneliness, Sadness}	0.4268293	0.9722222	1.138889
6 {CEAS_Q4=Guilt, CEAS_Q11=Nervousness, Rebellion, Shooting.}	{CEAS_Q13=Hopelessness, Loneliness, Sadness}	0.4146341	0.9714286	1.137959
8 {CEAS_Q22..JOY.=1, well_being=MID}	=> {CEAS_Q13=Hopelessness, Loneliness, Sadness}	0.5000000	0.9318182	1.091558

To extract relations between emotionality and images, a linear regression model was used because of the possibility of presenting statistical significance through p. The p-value is defined as the probability of obtaining an effect equal to what was actually observable when the zero hypothesis is true.

To shape the values of each subset of each image, the emotionality index has a specific role. The aim is to find out to what extent this role exists.

The base measurement (p-value) steps are:

- Very High Significance
- High Significance
- Normal Significance
- Limit Importance
- Not at all important

Image 14	Image 29
Normal significance in the "Concern" index	Marginal significance in the Relaxation Index
Image 15	Image 30
Normal significance in the "Fear" index and high significance in the "Anger" index	Normal significance in the "Aggressiveness" index
Image 16	Image 31
Normal significance in the index "Abnormality"	Normal significance in the "Enthusiasm" index and the "Inconvenience" index
Image 17	Image 32
Normal significance in the "indifference" index and high significance in the index "Disgust"	Marginal significance in the "Enthusiasm" index and normal significance in the "Discomfort" index
Image 18	Image 33
No significance	High significance in the "Enthusiasm" index and the "Inconvenience" index
Image 23	Image 34
No significance	Marginal significance in the "Infertility" index
Image 24	Image 35
Marginal significance in the "Fraud" index and high significance in the "Anger" index	No significance
Image 25	Image 36
Marginal significance in the "Enthusiasm" index	No significance
Image 26	Image 37
Normal significance in the "Infertility" index	Normal significance in the "Enthusiasm" index
Image 27	Image 38
Normal significance in the "Enthusiasm" index	Normal significance in the "Infertility" index
Image 28	Image 39
No significance	Normal significance in the "Enthusiasm" index

4. CONCLUSION

One general determination of the results can be exported in order to conclude and explain the consumer behavior of young adults in social networks. This paper can be a useful tool in the field of Marketing in order to decode psychological issues of young adulthood in the sector of emotional ability, personality and empathy between males and females.

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